

three N levels in a randomized block design with four replications. P and K (17.5 kg P, 33 kg K/ha) were constant for all treatments, including control.

Chemical analysis established 4% N content of azolla, based on dry weight. Azolla inoculated at 1 t/ha at transplanting, with 3.5 kg P/ha, recorded a fresh weight of 5 t/ha at incorporation 20 d after transplanting.

In the wet season, yields with N fertilizer were consistently higher than that of control (see table).

Yield with fresh azolla inoculated at 1 t/ha with 3.5 kg P/ha and incorporated 20 d after inoculation were equal to yields with 5 t fresh azolla/ha incorporated before planting.

In the dry season, yields with 90 kg N/ha were significantly higher than in all other treatments. Azolla at 5 t/ha yielded 0.6 t/ha more than control.

The actual benefit of azolla in combination with fertilizer was rather inconsistent. But azolla alone showed significantly higher yields than control. This study suggests alternative fertilizer strategies when chemical fertilizers are scarce or expensive. □

Effect of azolla alone and in combination with N fertilizers on rice yield.^a Orissa, India, 1983.

Treatment per hectare	Yield ^a (t/ha)	Difference
<i>Wet season</i>		
90 kg N	3.7	1.8
60 kg N	3.5	1.6
30 kg N	3.3	1.4
10 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.3	1.4
10 t azolla	3.2	1.3
5 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.1	1.2
1 t azolla + 3.5 kg P	2.6	0.7
5 t azolla inoculated and incorporated at 20 DT ^b	2.6	0.7
Control	1.9	—
CD (0.05)	0.2	—
CV (%)	6	—
<i>Dry season</i>		
90 kg N	3.8	2.0
60 kg N	3.5	1.6
10 t azolla + 60 kg N	3.4	1.6
5 t azolla + 30 kg N	3.1	1.3
10 t azolla	3.1	1.3
30 kg N	3.0	1.1
1 t azolla + 3.5 kg P	2.8	0.9
5 t azolla	2.4	0.6
Control	1.8	—
CD (0.05)	0.1	—
CV (%)	4	—

^aMeans of 3 yr, 1983-86. ^bDays after transplanting.

Effect of gypsum and pyrite with different moisture regimes on sodic soil improvement and rice yield

S. K. Dubey, R. C. Mondal, and A. Swarup, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Karnal 132001, India

We evaluated the effect of adding 7.25 meq gypsum/100 g soil (50% G.R.) and pyrite equivalent to gypsum on sulfur basis at 3 moisture regimes (continuous saturation [CS], continuous flooding [CF], and alternate saturation and flooding [ASF]) on the improvement of sodic soil and on yield in a pot with 3 replications. Soil was highly sodic, with pH 10.6, exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) 95, exchangeable Ca + Mg 0.45 meq/100 g soil, organic C 0.22%, CaCO₃, 2.75%, CEC 10.0

meq/100 g soil, and gypsum requirement 14.5 meq/100 g soil.

Gypsum and pyrite were added to soil in 10-kg glazed clay pots 2 wk before transplanting 30-d-old Pusa 2-21 seedlings. The moisture regimes were maintained from transplanting to crop maturity. Urea at 80 ppm N and zinc sulfate at 4.5 ppm Zn were applied — half the N and all the Zn at transplanting, the remaining N topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after transplanting.

Gypsum was better than pyrite in improving soil and yield of rice at all three moisture regimes. While CF proved more effective when gypsum was applied, ASF did better with pyrite (Table 1, 2). Growing of rice under CF facilitated greater sodic soil improvement. □

Table 1. Effect of gypsum and pyrite at 3 moisture regimes on soil pH and ESP after rice harvest. Karnal, India.

Moisture regime	pH (1:2) soil water			ESP		
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite
Continuous saturation	10.40	9.20	9.70	81.5	41.2	51.8
Alternate saturation – flooding	10.35	9.00	9.40	78.4	36.1	48.5
Continuous flooding	10.35	8.80	9.90	79.7	25.4	65.2

Table 2. Effect of gypsum and pyrite at 3 moisture regimes on rice grain yield.^a Karnal, India.

Moisture regime	Grain yield (g/pot)			
	Control	Gypsum	Pyrite	Mean
Continuous saturation	1.10	12.67	5.77	6.51
Alternate saturation – flooding	1.47	14.87	8.40	8.24
Continuous flooding	1.93	18.40	4.13	8.15
Mean	1.50	15.31	6.10	

^aCD at P = 0.05: amendments = 0.72, moisture regimes = 0.72, amendments × moisture regimes = 1.25.

Availability to wetland rice of nitrogen from cattle manure

Y. Singh, B. Singh, M.S. Maskina, and O. P. Meelu, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

Mineralization and availability of N from organic manure will be affected by its C-to-N ratio, soil management, and climatic conditions. Since only a part of organic N will be mineralized during the

growing season of rice, a residual effect of manures is expected in the following crop. We compared the availability of N from cattle manure with urea N to wetland rice. Residual effect was evaluated in a following wheat crop.

Soil of the experimental field was a Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.6, 0.34% organic C, 0.05% total N, and a water percolation rate of 4.5 mm/h. Treatments were 4 rates of N (0, 60, 120,

Rice grain yield and N uptake response to urea N and proportions of total N from applied cattle manure. Ludhiana, India.

Effect of urea and cattle manure N on P and K uptake of rice and the residual effect on soil properties and wheat yield. Ludhiana, India.

	Rates of N (kg/ha)				LSD (P=0.05)
	0	60	120	180	
<i>N application to rice</i>					
Urea	14	21	25	27	5.6
Cattle manure	14	15	21	24	
<i>K uptake of rice (kg/ha)</i>					
Urea	71	129	140	155	10.2
Cattle manure	71	87	93	149	
<i>Soil organic C (%)</i>					
Urea	0.34	0.35	0.36	0.36	0.03
Cattle manure	0.34	0.35	0.39	0.41	
<i>Olsen P (kg/ha)</i>					
Urea	22	20	13	12	3.6
Cattle manure	22	18	19	21	
<i>P application to wheat</i>					
<i>Wheat grain yield (t/ha) on soil amended with cattle manure</i>					
No P	3.2	3.5	3.6	3.8	0.21
26 kg P/ha	3.6	3.8	3.8	3.9	

and 180 kg/ha) applied through urea and through cattle manure. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. The cattle manure contained 1.3% total N, 0.38% total P, and had 26:1 C:N.

Cattle manure was incorporated into the soil 1 d before transplanting rice. Urea was applied in 3 equal splits at 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting. A basal dose of 13 kg P and 5 kg Zn/ha also was applied to rice. Variety PR106 was

transplanted 24 Jun 1986.

After harvest, all plots were subdivided to accommodate 2 levels of P (0 and 26 kg/ha). Wheat was fertilized with a uniform 80 kg N and 25 kg K/ha.

Both urea and manure N increased rice grain yield and N uptake significantly (see figure). Quadratic response curves were fitted to the rice grain yield and N uptake by considering different proportions of the cattle manure N to be as good as urea N. The regression analysis showed that 45% of

the N applied as cattle manure and urea N had effects on grain yield; 40% of N as cattle manure and urea N produced similar effects on N uptake by rice. The lower values for N uptake than for grain yield suggest that cattle manure N was more efficiently translated into rice grain yield than was urea N. Both P and K uptake of rice increased significantly with the application of either urea and cattle manure N (see table). Soil organic C content increased only when cattle manure was applied at high rates.

While Olsen P decreased significantly with urea N treatments, with cattle manure it maintained its initial level. Since both organic C and Olsen P contents were higher in soil amended with cattle manure, grain yield of the following wheat crop increased significantly. At 120 and 180 kg N/ha as cattle manure applied to rice, the wheat crop did not respond to direct P application. □

Effect of soil bulk density and soil texture on root growth

I. Meerigama, B. V.R. Punyawardena, and L. G.G. Yapa, Soil Science Department, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Peradeniya, Sri Lanka

We studied root growth of rice variety H4 at different soil bulk density and soil texture levels. The soil was a sandy loam (Rhodustalf, 19% clay, 11% silt, and 70% sand) from the central region of Sri Lanka. The texture was changed by adding medium sand in a ratio of 1:5 (sand:soil).

Soils were incubated 2 wk at 12% moisture and compacted in PVC cylinders (height and diameter 0.1 m) to a height of 7.5 cm, creating 3 levels of bulk density (1.15, 1.30, and 1.45 Mg/m³).

Ten pregerminated seeds were planted in each compacted soil column and covered with 1 cm layer of the same soil. Cores were covered with polyethylene and placed randomly in a large polyethylene chamber to minimize moisture loss. Root tips which